

THE INFLUENCE OF SELF-REGULATED LEARNING AND TEACHER AUTONOMY SUPPORT ON THE PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS AMONG FIRST YEAR FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT STUDENTS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 7

Pages: 1122-1139

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2898

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14628682

Manuscript Accepted: 12-17-2024

The Influence of Self-Regulated Learning and Teacher Autonomy Support on the Problem-Solving Skills among First Year Financial Management Students

Princess Kaye B. Martinez,* Deveyvon L. Espinosa
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The purpose of the study was to determine the influence of self-regulated learning and teacher autonomy support on the problem-solving skills among first year financial management students in a local college in Davao del Norte. A sample of 177 randomly selected first year financial management students who were identified using stratified random sampling answered the surveys on the three variables. This study used the following statistical tools to obtain the results: mean, Pearson r , and regression. Results also revealed that there is a significant relationship between self-regulated learning and problem-solving skills. Likewise, there is also a significant relationship between teacher autonomy support and problem-solving skills. Moreover, results show that domains of self-regulated learning such as learning responsibility and organizing can significantly influence problem-solving skills. Finally, it was revealed that domains of teacher autonomy support such as providing choice, fostering understanding and interest, and allowing criticism and encouraging independent thinking cannot significantly predict the problem-solving skills of the respondents. Results imply that the variables did not influence problem-solving skills of first year financial management students.

Keywords: *self-regulated learning, teacher autonomy support, problem-solving skills, financial management students, Philippines*

Introduction

Connecting various mathematical concepts is essential for students to excel in solving math problems. These connections are akin to assembling puzzle pieces encompassing facts, concepts, rules, visual representations, and problem-solving skills. When students effectively link these elements, they are more likely to succeed in solving complex math problems. However, difficulties in making these connections or errors in linking them can significantly impede their problem-solving abilities, making math more challenging. In essence, students who are adept at integrating different mathematical ideas tend to perform better in problem-solving tasks (Pambudi et al., 2020).

In Indonesia, the PISA 2018 results revealed a concerning decline in education standards, particularly in mathematics, where the country ranked 73rd with an average score of just 379. This decline underscores a significant problem in the way mathematics is taught, as seen in schools in Dukupuntang State High School. The persistence of traditional teaching methods that do not prioritize problem-solving skills is critical issue. Teachers report that the lack of time to properly evaluate students' problem-solving skills further exacerbates the situation, contributing to the country's worsening performance in mathematics education (Tohir, 2019).

In the Philippines, there is a serious problem with students' problem-solving skills in mathematics. The Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) shows that only 19% of Filipino students meet the basic standard for math understanding, while a staggering 81% fall below this level. Research highlights that 40% of students struggle specifically with word problems, often make mistakes, misunderstanding the questions, mixing up numbers, or getting confused by unfamiliar terms (TIMSS, 2019).

This study is relevant because it delves into the connection between how students learn and their ability to solve real-world problems, particularly among first-year financial management students. Problem-solving skills are crucial in both business and everyday life. By exploring how self-regulated learning and teacher autonomy support influence these skills, the study can provide useful insights for improving teaching methods. Additionally, Filipino students scoring below the lowest proficiency level in the PISA indicates they have been fallen significantly behind in mathematics education. Most Filipino students lack the necessary problem-solving skills compared in other parts of the world.

In the realm of research, there is a noticeable gap when it comes to exploring how self-regulated learning and teacher autonomy support influence students' problem-solving skills within a specific context. In fact, Pratiwi et al. (2022) conducted a study entitled "The Role-Playing Problem-Posing Learning to Improve Students' Emotional Intelligence and Mathematics Problem-Solving Skills," which aims to explore how role-playing and problem-posing learning strategies can enhance both students' emotional intelligence and their ability to solve math problems. Another, a study entitled, "The Relationship Between Maths Anxiety, Attitude Towards Mathematics and Maths Problem-Solving Skills Among Primary Pupils in Kedah," by Alias et al. (2023) had conducted with the purpose of understanding the connections between these factors and how they influence primary pupils' ability to solve math problems. Further, a study entitled, "Investigating Critical Thinking in Prospective Teachers: Metacognitive Skills, Problem Solving Skills and Academic Self-Efficacy," was conducted to examine the relationship and how these factors contribute to the overall effectiveness of future educators in their teaching practices (Kozikoğlu, 2019).

The existing studies show the connections between the variables present in this paper. However, this study is exclusively unique from the aforementioned studies because there is no existing study that examine the self-regulated learning and teacher autonomy support on the problem-solving skills and the respondents were not financial management students, and were not conducted during the new learning modality. Hence, the aforementioned studies indicate that this current study does not show irrelevance and redundancy.

Finally, this study will contribute valuable information not just within the institution but also to a wider audience, including its findings, will be disseminated to the various research conferences and related agencies to facilitate scholarly exchange and utilization of research-based discovery. By doing this, the significance and findings of this study would be recognized by the broader community through making actions and solutions on the problems being discussed as well as the recommendations being suggested here.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study was to determine the significant relationship between self-regulated learning and teacher autonomy support on the problem-solving skills among first year financial management students. To be specific, this study sought answers to the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of self-regulated learning in terms of:
 - 1.1. memory strategy;
 - 1.2. goal setting;
 - 1.3. self-evaluation;
 - 1.4. seeking assistance;
 - 1.5. environmental structuring;
 - 1.6. learning responsibility; and
 - 1.7. organizing.
2. To determine the level of teacher autonomy support in terms of:
 - 2.1. providing choice;
 - 2.2. fostering understanding and interest; and
 - 2.3. allowing criticism and encouraging independent thinking.
3. To determine the level of problem-solving skills:
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. self-regulated learning and problem-solving skills; and
 - 4.2. teacher autonomy support and problem-solving skills.
5. To determine which domain/s of self-regulated learning and teacher autonomy support that can consistently influence the problem-solving skills of the first year financial management students.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a quantitative approach, which means it measure the problem by collecting numerical data or data that could be turned into useful statistics. Quantitative research is defined as a method for testing objective ideas by exploring the relationship between variables. These variables measured using tools and instruments, and the resulting data is analyzed using statistical methods and structured approaches like surveys. Statistical data typically involves gathering numerical information and analyzing the findings, which help determine the best course of action (Apuke, 2017).

In the context of this study, quantitative research was employed because it allows for the precise measurement and statistical analysis of variables. This approach enables the identification of patterns, correlations, and potential causal relationships between self-regulated learning, teacher autonomy support, and problem-solving skills. By using standardized instruments and large sample sizes, quantitative research ensures the reliability and generalizability of the findings. Additionally, it facilitates the objective evaluation of hypotheses, contributing to a clearer understanding of the factors influencing problem-solving skills among the specific population.

Moreover, the descriptive-correlational research approach, which falls under quantitative methods, involved gathering and analyzing data related to a specific subject without directly intervening or influencing the subjects being studied. This approach was chosen to gain a comprehensive understanding of the complex relationships between variables within the study's context. In scientific investigations, this method was used to carefully observe and record behaviors and characteristics of both the phenomenon being studied and the research participants (Dudovskiy, 2018). Furthermore, according to Williams (2022), the descriptive-correlational research approach was an investigation where the collected and organized data could be represented by numbers.

In this study, a descriptive correlational design was used to measure and describe the relationships between self-regulated learning, teacher autonomy support, and problem-solving skills. By observing and analyzing the degree of association between these variables without manipulating them, the study could reveal patterns and trends, such as whether certain self-regulated learning are linked to higher or lower levels of problem-solving skills, or how teacher autonomy support influences students' problem-solving skills.

Respondents

The respondents of this study are first year financial management students from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST) during the first semester of A.Y. 2023-2024. They are chosen as the respondents because the study is about self-regulated learning and problem-solving skills on teacher autonomy support of students. Since the study's purpose involved problem-solving skills, choosing first year financial management students would have been fitting and valid. Further, to establish randomness and maintain the element of science in the study, stratified random sampling is chosen.

Further, Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents of this study. To make sure the samples are distributed accurately, the researcher used a method called stratified random sampling with proportional allocation. This involves dividing the total group, in this case, the first-year financial management students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST), into smaller groups or "strata." From each of these groups, samples are randomly chosen using a consistent method. The samples from each group are then combined to create the overall stratified random sample. This approach aims to provide a representative and reliable representation of the entire first-year financial management student population at KCAST, and the researcher will use Slovin's formula with a margin of error of 0.05 to determine the sample size (Nguyen et al., 2020).

In addition, the total respondents of the study which were taken mainly from five sections of first year financial management students. Among 317 total population of first year financial management students of the institution, 64 are from the section 1A, 63 are from the section 1B, 63 are from the section 1C, 62 are from the section 1D, and 65 are from the section 1E.

To ensure an appropriate sample for the study, the statistician calculated the sample size, resulting in the selection of 36 out of 64 students from BSBA Financial Management section 1A, 35 out of 63 students from BSBA Financial Management section 1B, 35 out of 63 students from BSBA Financial Management section 1C, 35 out of 62 students from BSBA Financial Management section 1D, and 36 out of 65 students from BSBA Financial Management section 1E. In total, 177 were sampled out of 317 first year financial management.

The criteria of selecting the respondents are the following: the respondents must be enrolled in the first semester of the academic year 2023-2024 under BSBA- Financial Management program in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. Also, must have sufficient engagement in learning mathematics in their junior and senior high school years.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Program</i>	<i>Section</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
BSBA-Financial Management	1A	64	36	11%
BSBA-Financial Management	1B	63	35	11%
BSBA-Financial Management	1C	63	35	11%
BSBA-Financial Management	1D	62	35	11%
BSBA-Financial Management	1E	65	36	11%
Total		317	177	56%

Instrument

The study employed a five-point Likert scale to assess respondents' observation levels for the three variables. The five-point Likert scale was adopted and modified from the study of Adelson and McCoach (2010) such that this study modified it to Frequency Likert scale having the following interpretation of values: 5 – Always, 4 – Oftentimes, 3 – Sometimes, 2 – Seldom, and 1 – Never. The researcher found it relevant to use the scale in this study since 5-point Likert scales are globally considered reliable scales in measuring perceptions, behavior, and attitudes (Sullivan & Artino, 2013).

Also, the dependent variable in this study, was measure using a multiple-choice question format. Multiple Choice Questions (MCQs) are widely acknowledged as the most versatile and effective type of objective test items. They are capable of assessing essential educational outcomes, including knowledge, understanding, judgement, and problem-solving skills (Al-Rukban, 2006).

The study adopted three questionnaires from web sources to measure the variables. The instrument for self-regulated learning is from the study of Carlo Magno (2010) entitled *Assessing Academic Self-Regulated Learning Among Filipino College Students*. The self-regulated learning questionnaire have seven indicators: memory strategy with five items, goal setting with five items, self-evaluation with five items, seeking assistance with five items, environmental structuring with five items, learning responsibility with five items, and organizing with five items. In describing the self- regulated learning questionnaire, the following five-point scale was used.

Further, for the instrument for Teacher Autonomy Support is from study of Assor et al (2002) entitled *Choice is Good, but Relevance is Excellent: Autonomy- Enhancing and Suppressing Teacher Behaviours Predicting Students' Engagement in Schoolwork*. The teacher autonomy support questionnaire has three indicators: providing choice with five items, fostering understanding and interest with four items, and allowing criticism and encouraging independent thinking with five items. In describing teacher autonomy support questionnaire, the following five-point scale will be used.

Moreover, the instrument for problem-solving skills is adapted from the study of Asoy and Dagohoy (2023) which is *Assessing the*

Factors of Academic Achievement in Mathematics in the Modern World Using Structural Equation Modeling. The problem-solving skills employed research instruments conducted with students was the problem-solving test questionnaire. The problem-solving test consisted of 25 questions, which was a multiple-choice test. The problem-solving test has a full score of 25 points. Every correct answer on each item corresponds to 1 point. Higher scores indicate higher problem-solving skills.

Procedure

In gathering data, the researchers took the following steps.

Questionnaire Development. The researcher searched the questionnaires drawn from journal articles related to the three variables.

Revision and Validation of Questionnaires. After forming the questionnaire, it was used and submitted to a panel of experts for evaluation and contextualization. The researcher follows the advice of those revision experts until it was approved for use.

Requesting Approval to Carry out the Study. The researcher asked for permission to conduct this from the vice president of academic affairs at the research locale through a formal letter. The letter was signed by the researcher himself and noted by his research adviser and the director for research and development.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. Survey questionnaires in printed forms were distributed individually to the respondents, who are second to fourth-year mathematics students roaming around the campus.

Collection and Tabulation of the Data. After the survey, the researcher took and analyzed the research instrument to record the collected data from the respondents. The statistical data were analyzed, and the findings were subsequently interpreted. Based on the final data set, conclusions were drawn, and recommendations were formulated in accordance with the results of the learning assessment.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in the computation of data and testing the hypothesis. It includes mean, Pearson r, and regression.

Mean. This was used to determine the level of self-regulated learning, problem-solving skills, and teacher autonomy support.

Pearson r. This was used to test the relationship between self-regulated learning and problem-solving skills, and teacher autonomy support and problem-solving skills among first year financial management students.

Regression. This was used to identify the specific area or domain within self-regulated learning and teacher autonomy support that has a statistically significant influence on the problem-solving skills of first year financial management students.

Ethical Considerations

The participants in this study were first year financial management students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. The researcher took measures to ensure the safety, rights and trust of the participants, treating both the researcher and the study's objectives with fairness and care. It is crucial to maintain high ethical standards when conducting research with participants. In this quantitative study, the main focus is to uphold ethical integrity and prioritize the well-being of the participants. The researcher followed three fundamental principles: informed consent; risk of harm, maintaining confidentiality, and anonymity; and conflict of interest – were incorporated in this study according to the ethical criteria set by Denzin and Lincoln (2011).

Informed consent is the first core principle of ethical considerations. Participants will be fully informed about the study's requirements, how their data will be used, and any possible consequences. They will give their clear, active, and written consent to take part in the research. They will also know that they can access their information and can withdraw their consent whenever they want. The researcher and the participants can come to an agreement when seeking this informed consent, as suggested (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In this approach, the researcher includes an additional question in the consent letter, asking first year financial management students if they agree to participate in the study after being fully informed about any potential risks involved. Participants have option to decline if they feel uncertain or uncomfortable. The primary goal is to ensure that they clearly understand the study and willing to participate voluntarily. The researcher will ensure that all student respondent is genuinely enthusiastic and willing to contribute. Moreover, during data collection, it is crucial to ensure that participants' responses are based on the provided questionnaires.

Risk of Harm, Maintaining Confidentiality, and Anonymity is the second core of ethical considerations. This is about making sure that the participants are safe. It means that even the person doing the research cannot figure out who the participants are based on the information they provide. It also means not telling anyone who is not supposed to know about the participants' identities (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

Furthermore, it is utmost importance that the researcher takes significant measures to prioritize the safety and privacy of the first year financial management students, fully acknowledging their significance in the research endeavor. In order to guarantee complete anonymity of the collected data, the researcher has diligently removes any details that could potentially reveal the identity of the participants, including names. This ensures that no information remains that could be used to trace the responses back to specific

individuals, and any identifying information will be securely stored in separate and protected files.

Conflict of Interest is the third core aspect of ethical considerations. This concept acknowledges that a researcher's prior relationships or activities could lead to a situation where their personal interest might conflict with their research duties. In such cases, it is crucial to be transparent and disclose these conflicts when seeking ethics approval.

This allows the ethics committee to provide guidance on how to handle these conflicts. Additionally, conflicts of interest occur when a person prioritizes their personal interests over their responsibilities as a researcher or when it appears that they are doing so. These conflicts can be real, potential, or just perceived and may involve incentives such as money or other rewards. Conflicts of interest have the potential to affect a researcher's objectivity and judgement, which can undermine the credibility of their findings (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

From this perspective, there are no external factors involving the researcher that could influence the results of the research because the participants are also first year financial management students, and the researcher does not have any personal interest at stake in this study. Conflict of interest only becomes issue when the researcher has the ability to pressure participants into taking part through methods like blackmail, withholding benefits, or other forms of punishment.

Results and Discussion

Presented in this section below are the discussions of the data on self-regulated learning and teacher autonomy support on the problem-solving skills among first year financial management students. This chapter presents the data results on the level of self-regulated learning; the level of teacher autonomy support; and the level of problem-solving skills. This also includes the following: significant relationship between self-regulated learning and problem-solving skills; significant relationship between teacher autonomy support and problem-solving skills; and the significant influence between self-regulated learning and problem-solving skills; and the significant influence between teacher autonomy support and problem-solving skills. The presentations were done in parallel with the research objectives.

Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Memory Strategy

The level of self-regulated learning was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, memory strategy. The responses of the involved students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 2 is the level of self-regulated learning in terms of memory strategy. The data revealed that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of memory strategy had a total mean of 3.46 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of memory strategy is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.79 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 1— Using note cards to write information I need to remember.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.19 which descriptively means moderate. This implies that the item is sometimes manifested by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 4—Using graphic organizers to put abstract information into a concrete form.

Table 2. *Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Memory Strategy*

<i>Memory Strategy</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Using note cards to write information I need to remember	3.79	High
2. Making list of related information by categories	3.55	High
3. Rewriting class notes by rearranging the information in my own words	3.55	High
4. Using graphic organizers to put abstract information into a concrete form	3.19	Moderate
5. Representing concepts with symbols such as drawings so I can easily remember them	3.25	Moderate
Overall	3.46	High

Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Goal Setting

The level of self-regulated learning was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, goal setting. The responses of first year financial management students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 3. *Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Goal Setting*

<i>Goal Setting</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Making detailed schedule of my daily activities	3.66	High
2. Making a timetable of all the activities I have to complete	3.63	High
3. Planning things I have to do in a week	3.72	High
4. Using a planner to keep track of what I am supposed to accomplish	3.50	High
5. Keeping track of everything I have to do in a notebook or an a calendar	3.39	Moderate
Overall	3.58	High

Presented in Table 3 is the level of self-regulated learning in terms of goal setting. The data revealed that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of goal setting had a total mean of 3.58 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of goal setting is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.72 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 3— Planning things I have to do in a week.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.39 which descriptively means moderate. This means that the item is sometimes manifested by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 5—Keeping track of everything I have to do in a notebook or an a calendar.

Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Self-Evaluation

The level of self-regulated learning was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, self-evaluation. The responses of first year financial management students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 4 is the level of self-regulated learning in terms of self- evaluation. The data revealed that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of self- evaluation had total mean of 3.72 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of self-evaluation is oftentimes manifested.

Table 4. *Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Self-Evaluation*

<i>Self-Evaluation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Inquiring assistance from an expert if I am having a difficulty	3.77	High
2. Welcoming peer evaluations for every output	3.62	High
3. Evaluating my accomplishments at the end of each study session	3.65	High
4. Asking others how my work is before passing it to my professors	3.86	High
5. Taking note of the improvements on what I do	3.68	High
Overall	3.72	High

The highest mean is 3.77 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 1— Inquiring assistance from an expert if I am having a difficulty.

On the other hand, the lowest mean is 3.62 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 2—Welcoming peer evaluations for every output.

Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Seeking Assistance

The level of self-regulated learning was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, seeking assistance. The responses of the selected first year financial management students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below. Presented in Table 5 is the level of self-regulated learning in terms of seeking assistance. The data revealed that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of seeking assistance had total mean of 3.87 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of seeking assistance is oftentimes manifested.

Table 5. *Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Seeking Assistance*

<i>Seeking Assistance</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Using a variety of sources in making my research papers	3.81	High
2. Using library resources to find the information that I need	3.58	High
3. Taking my own notes in class	4.11	High
4. Enjoying group works because we help one another	4.04	High
5. Calling a classmate about the homework that I missed	3.79	High
Overall	3.87	High

The highest mean is 4.11 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 3— Taking my own notes in class.

Meanwhile, the lowest mean is 3.58 which descriptively means high. This implies that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 2— Using library resources to find the information that I need.

Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Environmental Structuring

The level of self-regulated learning was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, environmental structuring. The responses of first year financial management students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 6 is the level of self-regulated learning in terms of environmental structuring. The data revealed that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of environmental structuring had total mean of 3.81 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of environmental structuring is oftentimes manifested.

Table 6. *Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Environmental Structuring*

<i>Environmental Structuring</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Avoiding watching television if I have a pending a homework	3.66	High
2. Isolating myself from unnecessary noisy places	3.84	High
3. Do not want to bear a single sound when I'm studying	3.81	High
4. Cannot study nor do my homework if the room is dark	3.86	High
5. Switching off my TV for me to concentrate on my studies	3.90	High
Overall	3.81	High

The highest mean is 3.90 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 5— Switching off my TV for me to concentrate on my studies. In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.66 which descriptively means high. This implies that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 1—Avoiding watching television if I have a pending a homework.

Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Learning Responsibility

The level of self-regulated learning was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, learning responsibility. The responses of first year financial management students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below. Presented in Table 7 is the level of self-regulated learning in terms of learning responsibility. The data revealed that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of learning responsibility had total mean of 4.02 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of learning responsibility is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 4.24 which descriptively means very high. This means that the item is always manifested by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 1— Rechecking my homework if I have done it correctly before passing. In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.82 which descriptively means high. This implies that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 2—Do things as soon as the teacher gives the task.

Table 7. *Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Learning Responsibility*

<i>Learning Responsibility</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Rechecking my homework if I have done it correctly before passing	4.24	High
2. Do things as soon as the teacher gives the task	3.82	High
3. Am concerned with the deadlines set by the teachers.	4.12	High
4. Prioritizing my schoolwork over other activities.	3.97	High
5. Finishing all my homework first before doing unnecessary things.	3.95	High
Overall	4.02	High

Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Organizing

The level of self-regulated learning was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, organizing. The responses of first year financial management students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 8 is the level of self-regulated learning in terms of organizing. The data revealed that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of organizing had total mean of 3.99 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of organizing is oftentimes manifested.

Table 8. *Level of Self-Regulated Learning in Terms of Organizing*

<i>Organizing</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Highlighting important concepts and information I find in my readings	4.14	High
2. Picturing in my mind how the test will look like based on previous tests	3.81	High
3. Putting my past notebooks, handouts, and the like in a certain container	3.71	High
4. Studying at my own pace	4.16	High
5. Fixing my things first before I start studying	4.11	High
Overall	3.99	High

The highest mean is 4.16 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 4— Highlighting important concepts and information I find in my readings. In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.71 which descriptively means high. This implies that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 3—Putting my past notebooks, handouts, and the like in a certain container.

Summary on the Level of Self-Regulated Learning

Presented in Table 9 is the overall level of self-regulated learning in terms of memory strategy, goal setting, self-evaluation, seeking assistance, environmental structuring, learning responsibility and organizing.

Table 9. *Summary on the Level of Self-Regulated Learning*

<i>Self-Regulated Learning</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Memory Strategy	3.46	High
Goal Setting	3.58	High
Self-Evaluation	3.72	High
Seeking Assistance	3.87	High
Environmental Structuring	3.81	High
Learning Responsibility	4.02	High
Organizing	3.99	High
Overall	3.77	High

The data revealed that the level of self-regulated learning of first year financial management students has a total mean of 3.77 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of self-regulated learning as perceived by the students is oftentimes manifested.

Further, the highest mean is 4.02 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of learning responsibility is most oftentimes manifested among the seven domains.

In contrast, the lowest indicator is memory strategy which obtained a mean of 3.46 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicates that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of memory strategy is the least sometimes manifested among the seven domains.

Additionally, goal setting domain obtained a mean of 3.58 which means high, self-evaluation domain obtained a mean of 3.72 which means high, environmental structuring domain obtained a mean of 3.81 which means high, seeking assistance domain obtained a mean of 3.87 which means high, and organizing domain obtained a mean of 3.99 which means high. This indicates that the level of self-regulated learning in terms of goal setting, self-evaluation, environmental structuring, seeking assistance and organizing is oftentimes manifested.

Level of Teacher Autonomy Support in Terms of Providing Choice

The level of teacher autonomy support was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, providing choice. The responses of the involved students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 10 is the level of teacher autonomy support of first year financial management students in terms of providing choice. The data revealed that the level of teacher autonomy support in terms of providing choice has a total mean of 3.72 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This implies that the level of teacher autonomy support of first year financial management students in terms of providing choice is oftentimes observed.

Table 10. *Level of Teacher Autonomy Support in Terms of Providing Choice*

<i>Providing Choice</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Giving me enough time to finish it when I am doing something that interested me	4.01	High
2. Allowing me to choose how to do my work in the classroom	3.73	High
3. Asking me which topic I would like to study more and which I prefer to study less	3.64	High
4. Asking me if there are things I would like to change in the way I study	3.63	High
5. Allowing me to choose to study topics that interest me	3.59	High
Overall	3.72	High

The highest mean is 4.08 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 3— Explaining why it is important to study certain subjects in school.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.92 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by the respondents. This is from item no. 4—Talking to me about how I feel connecting the subjects I study.

Level of Teacher Autonomy Support in Terms of Allowing Criticism and Encouraging Independent Thinking

The level of teacher autonomy was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, allowing criticism and encouraging independent thinking. The responses of first year financial management students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 12 is the level of teacher autonomy of first year financial management students in terms of allowing criticism and encouraging independent thinking.

The data revealed that the level of teacher autonomy in terms of allowing criticism and encouraging independent thinking has a total mean of 4.02 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of teacher autonomy of first independent thinking strategy is oftentimes observed.

The highest mean 4.07 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by the respondents. This is from item no. 3—Is willing to listen to students complaints regarding him/her, and item no.4—Respects students who tell her what they really think and are not ingratiating.

Table 12. *Level of Teacher Autonomy Support in Terms of Allowing Criticism and Encouraging Independent Thinking*

<i>Allowing Criticism and Encouraging Independent Thinking</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Listening to my opinions and ideas	4.02	High
2. Telling me that if I do not agree with him/her, it is important that I would express my disagreement	3.93	High
3. Is willing to listen to students complaints regarding him/her	4.07	High
4. Respecting students who tell her what they really think and are not ingratiating	4.07	High
5. Allowing me to decide about things to myself	4.02	High
Overall	4.02	High

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.93 which descriptively means high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 2—Telling me that if I do not agree with him/her, it is important that I would express my disagreement.

Summary on the Level of Teacher Autonomy Support

Presented in Table 13 is the overall level of teacher autonomy support in terms of providing choice, fostering understanding and interest, and allowing criticism and encouraging independent thinking.

Table 13. *Summary on the Level of Teacher Autonomy Support*

<i>Teacher Autonomy Support</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Providing Choice	3.72	High
Fostering Understanding and Interest	4.06	High
Allowing Criticism and Encouraging Independent Thinking	4.02	High
Overall	3.93	High

The data revealed that the level of teacher autonomy of first year financial management students has a total mean of 3.93 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of teacher autonomy of first year financial management students is oftentimes observed.

Further, the highest mean is 4.06 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of teacher autonomy support in terms of fostering understanding and interest is oftentimes observed.

In contrast, the lowest indicator is providing choice which obtained a mean of 3.72 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of teacher autonomy support in terms of providing choice is oftentimes observed.

Furthermore, the allowing criticism and encouraging independent thinking domain of teacher autonomy support obtained a mean of 4.02 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of teacher autonomy in terms of allowing criticism and encouraging independent thinking is oftentimes observed.

Level of Problem-Solving Skills

The level of problem-solving skills of first year financial management students was measured through a test questionnaire with 25 items covering the topics in the course, Mathematics in the Modern World. The response of the 177 respondents was presented and analyzed below.

The level of problem-solving skills of the first year financial management students is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The summary of the data is shown in Table 14. The data revealed an overall average score of 15.7 out of 25, or qualitatively interpreted as good. The highest score was 24 out of 25 which has obtained by 3 students or equivalent to 1.70%.

On the other hand, the lowest score was 3 and was obtained by 4 students or 2.26%. Additionally, the score with the highest frequency was 22 which was obtained by 24 students or equivalent to 13.56%.

Hence, the summary of results stipulates that the problem-solving skills of first year financial management students is satisfactory. This indicates that first year financial management students possess a foundational understanding of mathematics in the modern world concepts, yet still need further guidance and support to advance their skills in this area.

These students may face challenges in comprehending more complex advanced algebra, calculus for finance, statistical methods and financial modeling, highlighting the importance of providing additional practice and reinforcement to help them fully grasp the subject matter.

Table 14. *Level of Problem-Solving Skills*

<i>Data</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
3	4	2.26%		
4	1	0.57%		
5	3	1.70%		
6	12	6.78%		
7	5	2.83%		
8	10	5.65%		
9	5	2.83%		
10	4	2.26%		
11	7	3.96%		
12	6	3.40%		
13	5	2.83%		
14	3	1.70%		
15	6	3.39%	15.7	Very Good
16	9	5.09%		
17	7	3.96%		
18	9	5.09%		
19	14	7.91%		
20	18	10.17%		
21	14	7.91%		
22	24	13.56%		
23	8	4.52%		
24	3	1.70%		
Total	177	100%		

Legend: 1 – 5 Poor, 6 – 10 Fair, 11 – 15 Good, 16 – 20 Very Good, 21 – 25 Excellent

Significant Relationship between Self-Regulated Learning and Problem-Solving Skills

Presented in Table 15 is the result of the significant relationship between self-regulated learning and problem-solving skills, $r(175) = .217, p = .004$. Since the p -value (.004) is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis will be rejected in this context. Therefore, the relationship between self-regulated learning and problem-solving skills is positive and significant.

Table 15. *Significant relationship between Self-Regulated Learning and Problem-Solving Skills*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision @ = 0.05</i>
Self-Regulated Learning	3.78			
Problem-Solving Skills	15.69	.217	.004	Ho Rejected

Significant Relationship between Teacher Autonomy Support and Problem-Solving Skills

Presented in Table 16 is the result of the significant relationship between teacher-autonomy support and problem-solving skills, $r(175) = .135, p = .007$. Since the p -value (.007) is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis will be accepted in this context. Therefore, the relationship between teacher autonomy support and problem-solving skills is positive and significant.

Table 16. *Significant relationship between Teacher Autonomy Support and Problem-Solving Skills*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision @ = 0.05</i>
Teacher Autonomy Support	3.93			
Problem-Solving Skills	15.69	.135	.007	Ho Rejected

Domain/s of Self-Regulated Learning that can Considerably influence the Problem-Solving Skills

Presented in table 17 was the significant influence of the domain of learning responsibility that can considerably influence the problem-solving skills among first year financial management students. The results showed that learning responsibility, a domain of self-regulated learning, appear to be statistically significant predictor of the level of problem-solving skills among first year financial management students, ($\beta = 2.847, p < 0.001$), respectively at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the beta value indicates that for every units increase of the learning responsibility, the level of problem-solving skills among first year financial management students will also increase by 2.847 units.

Additionally, the results showed that organizing, a domain of self-regulated learning, appear to be statistically significant predictor of

the level of problem-solving skills among first year financial management students, ($\beta=-1.943$, $p<.001$), respectively at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the beta value indicates that for every units increase of the organizing, the level of problem-solving skills among first year financial management students will also decrease by -1.943 units.

On the other hand, the results showed that memory strategy, a domain of self-regulated learning, appear to be not statistically significant predictor of the level of problem-solving skills among first year financial management students, ($\beta=-0.196$, $p=0.796$), respectively at 0.05 level of significance, the p-values of the domain exceeded 0.05. This suggest that the domain which is memory strategy do not have significant influence on problem-solving skills of the students.

Table 17. Domain/s of Self-Regulated Learning that can Considerably Influence the Problem-Solving Skills

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		P-Value	Decision @=0.05
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	6.659	3.107				
Memory Strategy	-0.196	0.755	-0.026		0.796	Ho Accepted
Goal Setting	1.225	0.764	0.159		0.111	Ho Accepted
Self-Evaluation	1.234	0.773	0.162		0.113	Ho Accepted
Seeking Assistance	-0.55	0.945	-0.060		0.561	Ho Accepted
Environmental Structuring	-0.218	0.775	-0.027		0.779	Ho Accepted
Learning Responsibility	2.847	0.873	0.321		0.001	Ho Rejected
Organizing	-1.943	0.909	-0.222		0.034	Ho Rejected

Dependent Variable: Problem-Solving Skills

Note: $R=0.362$ $R^2=0.131$ $F\text{-ratio}=3.635$ $P\text{-value}<0.001$

Moreover, the result showed that goal setting, a domain of self-regulated learning, appear to be not statistically significant predictor of problem-solving skills among first year financial management students, ($\beta=1.225$, $p=0.111$), respectively at 0.05 level of significance, the p-values of the domain exceeds 0.05. This suggest that the domain which is goal setting do not have significant influence on problem-solving skills of the students.

Also, the results showed that self-evaluation, a domain of self-regulated learning, appear to be not statistically significant predictor of problem-solving skills of first year financial management students, ($\beta=1.234$, $p=0.113$), respectively at 0.05 level of significance, the p-values of the domain exceeds 0.05. This suggest that the domain which is self-evaluation do not have significant influence on problem-solving skills of the students.

Furthermore, the results showed that seeking assistance, appear to be not a statistically significant predictor of the level of problem-solving skills of first year financial management students, ($\beta=-0.550$, $p=0.561$), respectively at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted. This suggest that the domain which is seeking assistance do not have significant influence on problem-solving skills of the students.

Consequently, the p-value for the remaining domain, which is environmental structuring ($\beta=0.218$, $p=0.779$), appears not to be a statistically significant predictor of problem-solving skills of the students, respectively at the 0.05 level of significance, the p-value for this domain exceeds 0.05. This suggest that environmental structuring do not have a significant influence of problem-solving skills of the first year financial management students.

Therefore, self-regulated learning explained significant proportion of variance in problem-solving skills, $R^2=0.131$, $F=3.635$, $p<0.001$. The R^2 of 0.131 shows that the model predicts 13.1% of the statistical variation observed in the level of student's problem-solving skills among the respondents. The coefficient of alienation which 86.7% points to be extent at which other indicators or domains not included in the study may explain the variance observed in the level of students' problem-solving skills among the respondent.

Domain/s of Teacher Autonomy Support that can Considerably influence the Problem-Solving Skills Among First Year Financial Management Students

Presented in Table 18 was the significant influence of the domains of teacher autonomy support that can considerably influence the problem-solving skills among first year financial management students. No particular domain of teacher autonomy support can considerably influence the problem-solving skills among first year financial management students. Moreover, the results showed that providing choice, a domain of problem-solving skills, appear to be not statistically significant predictor of the level of problem-solving skills among first year financial management students, ($\beta=-0.049$, $p=0.954$), respectively at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted.

In addition, the p-value of remaining domain, which is fostering understanding ($\beta=1.262$, $p=0.177$) appear to be not statistically significant predictor of the problem-solving skills of the first year financial management students, respectively at 0.05 level of significance, the p-value of the domain exceeded 0.05. This suggest that the domain which is fostering understanding do not have significant influence on students' problem-solving skills.

Table 18. *Domain/s of Teacher Autonomy Support that can Considerably Influence the Problem- Solving Skills*

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	P- Value	Decision @=0.05
	Beta	Std. Error			
(Constant)	10.817	2.812			
Providing Choice	-0.049	0.842	-0.006	0.954	Ho Accepted
Fostering Understanding and Interest	1.262	0.931	0.158	0.177	Ho Accepted
Allowing Criticism and Encouraging Independent Thinking	-0.016	0.851	-0.002	0.985	Ho Accepted

Dependent Variable: Problem-Solving Skills

Note: $R=0.153$ $R^2=0.023$ $F\text{-ratio}=1.376$ $P\text{-value}=0.252$

Consequently, the p-value for the remaining domain, allowing criticism and encouraging independent thinking ($\beta=-0.016$, $p=0.985$), appears not to be statistically significant predictor of the problem-solving skills of the first year financial management students, respectively at 0.05 level of significance, the p-value for this domain exceeds 0.05. This suggest that allowing criticism and independent thinking do not have a significant influence on the problem-solving skills of the students.

Therefore, teacher autonomy support explained no significant proportion of the variance in problem-solving skills, $R^2=0.023$, $F=1.376$, $p<.252$. The R^2 of 0.023 shows that model predicts 2.3% of the statistical variation observed in the level of student's problem-solving skills among respondents. The coefficient of alienation which 97.7% points to the extent which other indicators or domains not included in the study may explain the variance observed in the level of students' problem-solving skills among the respondents.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, conclusions were drawn in answer to questions raised in the previous chapter. The respondents reported a high level of self- regulated learning which means that the variable is oftentimes observed by the students.

Based on the results in teacher autonomy support of first year financial management students, it can be also drawn that the level of teacher autonomy support among students was in high. This means that the students oftentimes observed the variable.

Moreover, based on the results in problem-solving skills of first year financial management students, it can be also drawn that the level of problem-solving skills of the students was in high. Also, this means that the students oftentimes observed the variable.

Overall correlation of two variables reveals a significant relationship between the two variables which was self-regulated learning and problem-solving skills of the first year financial management students. The study shows that the self-regulated learning has a high, positive, and significant relationship with problem-solving skills of the students, which means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

Overall correlation of two variables reveals a significant relationship between the two variables which was teacher autonomy support and problem-solving skills of first year financial management students. The study shows that the teacher autonomy has a high, positive, and significant relationship with problem-solving skills of the students, which means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected. Based on the result of regression analysis, two domains have shown significant influence to the self-regulated learning. This means that the domain – learning responsibility and organizing – is the significant predictor of problem-solving skills of the first year financial management students. This also indicates the rejection of the second null hypothesis proposed in the study. Accordingly, the model describes 13.1% of the statistical variation with an $F=3.635$ and $p<0.001$ in the level of problem-solving skills of the respondent, while the remaining 86.9% refers to other variables that have not been included in the study that may also affect the problem-solving skills of respondents.

Furthermore, based on the result of regression analysis, no domains have shown significant influence to the teacher autonomy support. This means that the three domains – providing choice, fostering understanding and interest, and allowing criticism and encouraging independent thinking– is not the significant predictor of problem-solving skills of the first year financial management students. This also indicates the rejection of the second null hypothesis proposed in the study. Accordingly, the model describes 2.3% of the statistical variation with values of $F=1.376$ and $p<0.001$ in the level problem-solving skills of the respondent, while the remaining 97.7% refers to other variables that have not been included in the study that may also affect the problem-solving skills of respondents.

Lastly, the findings from this study reaffirm the significance of self-regulated learning and problem-solving skills, supporting Miller's Information Processing Theory, which emphasizes how students manage and process information effectively to enhance learning outcomes. Additionally, the results align with Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory, highlighting that students' belief in their ability to succeed influences their approach to problem-solving and their persistence in challenging tasks. Moreover, Sweller's Cognitive Load Theory, which suggests that managing cognitive load is critical for effective learning, further anchors the study's findings by demonstrating how reducing cognitive load through autonomy support can improve problem-solving skills. Based on the results, this study firmly anchors the theories of Miller, Bandura, and Sweller in the context of reinforcing the importance of self-regulated learning, teacher autonomy support and problem-solving skills.

Based on the results, several recommendations were made to address problem-solving skills among first year financial management students:

Since the result of the self-regulated is high, it is hereby recommended that to continue employing strategies that foster independent learning, such as setting clear goals, monitoring progress, and employing effective study techniques. Additionally, it would be beneficial to explore further resources or support systems to enhance self-regulation skills and maintain this positive trajectory. Continuous reflection on learning processes and adapting strategies accordingly can further solidify success in self-regulated learning endeavors.

Subsequently, because the result of self-regulated learning in terms of goal setting, self-evaluation, seeking assistance, environmental structuring, learning responsibility and organizing is high, and only learning responsibility and organizing significantly predict the problem-solving skills of the students, it is hereby recommended to the educators should prioritize fostering these particular skills. It's imperative to design interventions and learning activities specifically targeting learning responsibility and organizing, aiming to enhance problem-solving abilities effectively. Additionally, continuous assessment and refinement of teaching methods to further bolster self-regulated learning can contribute significantly to improving overall academic outcomes and student success.

On the other hand, because the result of self-regulated learning in terms of memory strategy is moderate, it is crucial to delve deeper into understanding why this aspect is not as strong as others. Further research into effective memory-enhancing techniques tailored to the specific needs of financial management students could be beneficial. Additionally, providing targeted interventions or workshops focused on memory improvement within the financial management curriculum may help students bolster this area of self-regulated learning and enhance their overall academic performance.

Since the result of teacher autonomy support is high, it is hereby recommended to that the teacher to maintain and further cultivate this supportive approach. Educators should continue to maintain vigilance to ensure that such support is genuine and consistent. They should continuously assess their practices to ensure they are fostering true autonomy rather than simply appearing to do so. Additionally, teachers should remain open to feedback from students to ensure that their support is effectively empowering them in their learning journey.

Moreover, the result of teacher autonomy support in terms of providing choice, fostering understanding and interest, and allowing criticism and encouraging independent thinking is high. Thus, it is hereby recommended to further investigate the specific mechanisms through which these practices influence student outcomes. Conducting qualitative research, such as interviews or observations, could provide deeper insights into how teacher autonomy support impacts student engagement and learning processes. Additionally, exploring potential contextual factors that may affect the effectiveness of autonomy support interventions can inform more targeted and tailored approaches to promote student success.

Since the result of problem-solving skills is good, it is hereby recommended that the teachers critically evaluate the methods used to assess these skills to ensure they align with real-world challenges. Additionally, it would be beneficial for teachers to implement more complex problem-solving tasks to continuously challenge and further develop students' abilities. Regularly reviewing and updating teaching strategies based on student performance can also contribute to sustaining and also enhancing their problem-solving proficiency over time.

Overall, it can be seen that there is a correlation between self-regulated learning and problem-solving skills of first year financial management students. It is hereby recommended that the school institution and teachers to prioritize the integration of self-regulated learning techniques into the curriculum and teaching methods. Furthermore, fostering an environment that encourages students to develop and apply their problem-solving skills independently can lead to more effective learning outcomes and better preparation for their future careers in financial management. Moreover, it can be seen that there is a correlation between teacher autonomy support and problem-solving skills of first year financial management students. It is hereby recommended that the school institution and teachers to foster an environment that prioritizes autonomy and critical thinking. This can be achieved through professional development programs aimed at enhancing teachers' skills in autonomy support strategies. Additionally, creating opportunities for collaborative decision-making and student-led initiatives can further empower students to develop their problem-solving abilities, thereby enriching the overall educational experience.

Lastly, it is recommended for future researchers to explore the same topic using various methodologies, such as mixed methods, qualitative approaches, or case studies, in order to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the importance of the relationships between the variables. Additionally, it would be valuable for future studies to conduct mediation analysis to examine the relationship between teacher autonomy support and problem-solving skills. researcher should consider identifying and investigating potential mediating variables that might explain how or why teacher autonomy support influences problem-solving skills. This approach could provide deeper insights into the mechanisms underlying these relationships.

References

Abbassi, A., Hassaskhah, J., & Tahriri, A. (2018). The effect of teaching memory strategies on Iranian EFL learner's vocabulary retention in terms of learners' multiple intelligences. *International Journal of education & Literacy Studies*,

6(2). <https://journals.aiac.org.au/index.php/IJELS/article/view/4402/3431>

Ahmed, G., Tayyub, M., & Ismail, R. (2020) Effects of classroom environment for improving students' learning at secondary level in punjab province, pakistan. *Science Academique*, 1(1), 2-15. <https://scienceacademique.com/effects-of-classroom-environment-for-improving-students-learning-at-secondary-level-in-punjab-province-pakistan/>

Alias, Z, Jafar, M. F., & Kasim, M. (2023). The relationship between maths anxiety, attitude towards mathematics and maths problem-solving skills among primary school pupils in kedah. *International Journal of Modern Education*, 5(16), 28-40. <https://doi.org/10.35631/IJMEOE.516003>

Amalina, I. K., & Vidakovich, T. (2023). Development and differences in mathematical problem-solving skills: A cross-sectional study of differences in demographic backgrounds. *Heliyon*, 9(5). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16366>

Amiruddin, E. P. (2023). Memory strategies used by mathematics students at dayanu ikhsanuddin university. *International journal of Integrative Sciences*, 2(4), 499-512. <https://doi.org/10.55927/ijis.v2i4.v2i4.3759>.

Asoy, E. M., & Dagohoy, R. (2023). Assessing the Factors of Academic Achievement in Mathematics in the Modern World Using Structural Equation Modeling. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 6(2), 53-63. <https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v6i2.723>

Assor, A., Kaplan, H., & Roth, G. (2002). Choice is good, but relevance is excellent: Autonomy-enhancing and suppressing teacher behaviours predicting students' engagement in schoolwork. *British Journal of Educational Psychology* 72, 261-278. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709902158883>

Aydoğan, Y., & Özyürek, A. (2020). The relationship between problem-solving skills and memory development in preschool children. *Journal of History Culture and Art Research*, 9(3), 43-54. <https://doi.org/10.7596/taksad.v9i3.1988>

Ayish, N., & Deveci, T. (2019). Student perceptions of responsibility for their own learning and for supporting peers' learning in a project-based learning environment. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 31(2), 224-237. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1224347.pdf>

Bachmann, A. M. (2021). The effects of choice on student reading motivation. University of Houston. <https://uh-ir.tdl.org/collections/dee50d8d-4ac5-4a91-a16a-62217c150a4d>

Baker, C., Hjalmarson, M., & Fennell, F. (2022). Mathematics specialists as school-based leaders: Adapting responsibilities to address shifts in teaching and learning. *Investigating in Mathematics Learning*, 14(2), 134-150. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19477503.2022.2043664>

Baltaoğlu, M., & Güven, M. (2020). Views of prospective teachers on learning responsibility. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 7(1), 228-239. <https://doi.org/10.33200/ijcer.669055>

Bandura, A. (1993). Perceived self-efficacy in cognitive development and functioning. *Education Psychologist*, 28(2), 177-148. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326985ep2802_3

Benita, M., & Matos, L. (2021). Internalization of mastery goals: The differential effect of teachers' autonomy support and control. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.599303>

Bozkurt, E., & Yetkin Özdemir, I. E. (2023). Mathematics teachers' goal setting and planning activities in a lesson study context. *Hacettepe University Journal of Education*, 2535-4758. <https://doi.org/10.16986/HUJE.2023.498>

Brenner, C.A. (2022). Self-regulated learning, self-determination theory and teacher <https://slejournal.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40561-021-00184-5#citeas>

Brown, D., Barry, J., & Todd, B. (2020). Barriers to academic help-seeking: The relationship with gender-typed attitudes. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 45(3), 401-416. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2020.1774049>

Buzza, D., & Dol, M. (2015). Goal-setting support, motivation, and engagement in alternative math classes. *Exceptionality Education International*, 25(1), 35-66. <https://ojs.lib.uwo.ca/index.php/eei/article/view/7716/6332>

Callan, G., & Shim, S. (2019). How teachers define and identify self-regulated learning. *The Teacher Educator*, 54(3), 295-312. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08878730.2019.1609640>

Callan, G., Rubenstein, L., Barton, T., & Halterman, A. (2021). Enhancing motivation by developing cyclical self-regulated learning skills. *Theory Into Practice*, 61(1), 62-74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405841.2021.1932153>

Canvin, K., Macleod, C., Windle, G., & Sacker, A. (2018). Seeking assistance in later life: how do old people evaluate their need for assistance? Oxford University Press, 47, 466-473. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afx189>

Cerbito, A. F. (2020). Comparative analysis of mathematics proficiency and attitudes towards mathematics of senior high school

- student. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 10(5), 2250-3153. <https://doi.org/10.29322/IJSRP.10.05.2020.p10125>
- Chen, G., Marshall, S., & Horn, I. (2020). How do I choose?: Mathematics teachers' sense making about pedagogical responsibility. *Pedagogy, Culture & Society*, 29(3), 379-396. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681366.2020.1735497>
- Chen, J. K., Bradford, A., & Linn, M. (2020). Examining the impact of student choice in online science investigations. *International Society of the Learning Sciences*, 3, 1705-1708. <https://doi.org/10.22318/icsl2020.1705>
- Cho, M. K. & Kim, M. K. (2020). Investigating elementary students' problem solving and teacher scaffolding in solving an ill-structured problem. *International Journal of Education in Mathematics, Science and Technology*, 8(4), 274-289. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijemst.v8i4.1148>
- Colakoglu, T., Colakoglu, F. T., Senel, E. Gulsen, K., & Ozer, U. (2015). An investigation of the relationship between personality traits and problem solving skills of elite Turkish woman football players. *Anthropologist*, 19(2), 491-498. https://www.academia.edu/34239906/An_Investigation_of_the_Relationship_between_Personality_Traits_and_Problem_Solving
- Cox, J. (2019). Classroom management for an effective learning environment. Teach Hub. <https://www.teachhub.com/classroom-management/2019/05/classroom-management-for-an-effective-learning-environment/>
- Cronin, L., Marchant, D., Allen, J., Mulvenna, C., Cullen, D., Williams, G., & Ellison, P. (2019). Students' perceptions of autonomy-supportive versus controlling teaching and basic need satisfaction versus frustration in relation to life skills development in PE. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PSTCHSPORT.2019.05.003>
- Davidai, S., Deri, S., & Gilovich, T. (2020). There must be more to life than this: The impact of highly-accessible exemplars on self-evaluation and discontent. *Taylor & Francis Online*, 20, 79-93. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15298868.2020.1779121>
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.). (2011). *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*. sage. <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=AIRpMHgBYqIC&oi=fnd&pg=>
- Dewi, P. Y. A., & Primayana, K. H. (2019). Effect of learning module with setting contextual teaching and learning to increase the understanding of concepts. *International Journal of Education and Learning*, 1(1), 19-26. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/230039453.pdf>
- Fabricio, A. T., & Yassuda, M. S. (2011). Use of memory strategies among younger and older adults: Results from objective and subjective measures. *Dement Neuropsychologia*, 5(2), 93-98. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1980-57642011DN05020006>
- Felayabi, H., Purnawarman, P., & Sukyadi, D. (2022). Autonomy practiced by English primary school teachers to develop teaching professionalism. *Department of Education*, 9(1), 209-230. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1356598.pdf>
- Fitzmorris, R., Russo, S., Coristine, S., Rivolta, G., & Beninato, P. (2022, April 1). The importance of student-teacher relationships. *Classroom Practice in 2022*. <https://ecampusontario.pressbooks.pub/educ5202/chapter/the-importance-of-student-teacher-relationships/>
- Fleming, S., & Daw, N. (2017). Self-evaluation of decision-making: A general Bayesian framework for metacognitive computation. *Psychology Review* 124(1), 91-114. <https://doi.org/10.1037/rev0000045>
- Furlan, A., Galeazzo, A., & Paggiaro, A. (2019). Organizational and perceived learning in the workplace: A multilevel perspective on employees' problem solving. *Organization Science*, 30(2), 280-297. <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.2018.1274>
- Gok, G., & Boncukcu, G. (2023). The effect of problem-based learning on middle school students' environmental literacy and problem-solving skills. *Journal of Science Learning*, 6(4), 414-423. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1413606.pdf>
- Grove, M., Guiry, S., & Croft, T. (2018). Specialist and more-able mathematics students: Understanding their engagement with mathematics support. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 51(5), 643-668. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2019.1603407>
- Guinness, K., Detrich, R., Keyworth, R., & States, J. (2020). Overview of structured environment. Oakland, CA: The Wing Institute. <https://www.winginstitute.org/classroom-structured-environments>
- Hačatrdžana, L., & Linde, I. (2023). Piloting supplementary materials aimed at developing students' problem-solving and self-regulated learning skills. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 22(6), 475-493. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.22.6.25>
- Handoko, E., Gronseth, S., McNeil, S., Bonk, C., & robin, B. (2019). Goal setting and mooc completion: A study on the role of self-regulated learning in student performance in massive open online courses. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 20(3). <https://www.irrodl.org/index.php/irrodl/article/view/4270/5128>

- Healy, L., Smith, A., & Ntoumanis, N. (2018). Goal setting in sport and performance. *Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190236557.013.152>
- Jones, C., & Nillas, L. (2022). Fostering a respectful and engaging classroom environment. *John Wesley Powell Student Research Conference*, 3. <https://digitalcommons.iwu.edu/jwprc/2022/edstudies/3>
- Kaplan, A., Neuber, A., & Garner J. (2019). An identity perspective on high ability in self-regulated learning. *High Ability Studies*, 30, 53-78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13598139.2019.1568830>
- Kaplan, Z. (2023, March 23). What are the problem-solving skills? Definition and examples. *Forage*. <https://www.theforage.com/blog/skills/problem-solving-skills>
- Kolar, D. R. (2018). Students' self-evaluation in the context of practical pedagogical training. *International Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(1), 700-715. <https://doi.org/10.20319/pijss.2018.41.700715>
- Kopzhassarova, U., Akbeya, G., Eskazinova, Z., Belgibayeva, G., & Tazhikeyeva, A. (2016). Enhancement of students' independent learning through their critical skills development. *International Journal of Environmental & Science Education*, 11(18), <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311604567>
- Kozikoglu, I. (2019). Investigating critical thinking in prospective teachers: Metacognitive skills, problem solving skills and academic self-efficacy. *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, 10(2), 111-130. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/216567/>
- Kuhn, D. (2019). Critical thinking as discourse. *Human Development*, 62(3), 146-164. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000500171>
- Larmand, A. (2022, October, 23). The growing importance of student choice. *Edoporium*. <https://www.eduporium.com/blog/eduporium-weekly-the-importance-of-student-choice/>
- Larsen, S., & McCormick, K. (2022). Fostering professional responsibility through high-quality professional learning opportunities. *Teacher Development*, 26(1), 117-134. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13664530.2021.1982759>
- Lertyosbordin, C., Maneewan, S., & Srikaew, D. (2021). Components and indicators of problem-solving skills in robot programming activities. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 12(9). https://thesai.org/Downloads/Volume12No9/Paper_17-Components_and_Indicators_of_Problem_solving_Skills.pdf
- Lineweaver, T., Horhota, M., Crumley, J., Geanon, C., & Juett, J. (2018). Age differences in perceptions of memory strategy effectiveness for recent and remote memory. *Aging, Neuropsychology, and Cognition*, 25(2), 146-166. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13825585.2016.1269146>
- Ling, A. N. B., & Mahmud, M. S. (2023). Challenges of teachers when teaching sentence-based mathematics problem-solving skills. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1074202>
- Liu, H., Yao, M., Li, J., & Li, R. (2021). Multiple mediators in the relationship between perceived teacher autonomy support and student engagement in math and literacy learning. *Educational Psychology*, 41(2), 116-136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2020.1837346>
- Lovisa, S., David, S., & Milena T. Upper secondary school students' gendered self-evaluation in mathematics. *Twelfth Congress of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education*. <https://hal.science/hal-03745863/>
- Ma, Q. (2021). The role of teacher autonomy support on students' academic engagement and resilience. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.778581>
- Magno, C. (2010). Assessing academic self-regulated learning among filipino college students: The factor structure and item fit. *The International Journal of Educational and Psychological Assessment* 5.
- Magsino, L. (2021). Self-regulation learning variables and learners' performance: A correlational analysis. *International Review of Social Sciences Research*, 1(2), 34-57. https://iiari.org/journal_article/v1-2-150/
- Main, P. (2021). Embracing the learning theory: Constructivism. *Structural Learning*. <https://www.structural-learning.com/post/embracing-the-learning-theory-constructivism#:~:text=One%20of%20the%20key%20figures,new%20information%20on%20their%20own.>
- Marcera, A. (2020). Students' self-assessments on their problem-solving skills in basic calculus. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/355732739_Students'_Self-Assessments
- Merill, S., & Gonser, S. (2021). The importance of student choice across all grade levels. *Edutopia*. <https://www.edutopia.org/article/importance-student-choice-across-all-grade-levels/>
- Miller, G. A. (1956). The magical number seven, plus or minus two: Some limits on our capacity for processing information.

Psychological Review, 63(2), 81-97. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0043158>

Mulhayatiyah, D., Purwanti, P., Setya, W., Suhendi, H. Y., Kariadinata, R., & Hartini, S. (2019). The impact of digital learning module in improving students' problem-solving skills. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Fisika Al-BiRuNi*, 8(1), 11-22. <http://www.ejournal.radenintan.ac.id/index.php/al-biruni/article/view/3150/pdf>

Orhan, A. (2022). Critical thinking dispositions and decision making as predictors of high school students' perceived problem solving skills. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 115(4), 235-245. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00226071.2022.2113498>

Palengka, I., Juniati, D., & Abadi. (2022). Mathematical reasoning of prospective mathematics teachers in solving problems based on working memory capacity differences. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and technology education*, 18(12), 1305-8223. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/12670>

Pekdoğan, S., & Akgul, E. (2020). Decision-making as a predictor of problem-solving skills in 5-6-year-old children. *Journal of Education and Future*. <https://doi.org/10.30786/jef.635246>

Pambudi, D. S., Budayasa, I. K., & Lukito, A. (2020). The Role of mathematical connections in mathematical problem solving. *Journal Pendidikan Matematika*, 14(2), 129-144. <https://doi.org/10.22342/jpm.14.2.10985.129-144>

Pratiwi, D. J., Siswono, T. Y. E., & Mariana, N. (2022). The role-playing problem-posing learning to improve students' emotional intelligence and mathematics problem-solving skills. *International Journal of Recent Educational Research*, 3(3), 312-322. <https://journal.ia-education.com/index.php/ijorer/article/view/217/190>

Price, P., Jhangiani, R., & Chiang, I. (2014). *Research methods in psychology – 2nd Canadian Edition*. California State University, Fresno: Creative Commons Attribution NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International Licence.

Prodigy (2022). Why is math important? 9 reasons why math skills improve quality of life. Author. <https://www.prodigygame.com/main-en/blog/why-is-math-important/>

Richard. (2023, March 21). Why it's important to let children think for themselves when it comes to their education. Studybox. <https://studybox.london/author/infosimplywebsitesupport-co-uk/>

Razm, F., Hafezi, F., Marashian, F. S., Naderi, F., & Dashtbozorgi, Z. (2021). Effectiveness of flipped teaching and problem-solving methods on problem-solving ability and sense of responsibility among female high school students. according to the findings of a study. *Iranian Journal of Learning and Memory*. 3(12), 31-38. <https://doi.org/10.22034/iepa.2021.281955.1264>

Rovers, S., Clarebout, G., Saverberg, H. C., De Bruin, A., & Merrienboer, J. J. (2019). Granularity matters: comparing different ways of measuring self-regulated learning. *Metacognition and Learning*, 14, 1-19. <file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/s11409-019-09188-6.pdf>

Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55(1), 68-78. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.55.1.68>

Saraçoğlu, M., & Kahyaoğlu, M. (2021). Learning and studying approaches as a predictor of reflective thinking skills towards problem-solving of secondary school students. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*. 9(4), 132. <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.9n.4p.132>

Sari, E. P., & Karyati. (2020). CORE (Connecting, organizing, reflecting & extending) learning model to improve the ability of mathematical connections. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1581/1/012028>

Satyendra. (2023, October 15). Organizing – a management function. Ispat guru. <https://www.ispatguru.com/organizing-a-management-function/>

Selchan, K. (2023). Developing critical thinking skills: Empowering children for life and learning. *Linked In*. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/developing-critical-thinking-skills-empowering-children-selchan>

Setiyani, S., Fitriyani, N., & Sagita, L. (2020). Improving student's mathematical problem solving skills through quizizz. *Journal of Research and Advances in Mathematics Education* 5(3), 276-288. <https://doi.org/10.23917/jramathedu.v5i3.10696>

Sides, J., & Cuevas, J. (2020). Effect of goal setting for motivation, self-efficacy, and performance in elementary mathematics. *International Journal of Instructions*, 13(4).

Smith, C. (2019). Discourses of time and maturity structuring participation in mathematics and further mathematics. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 41(2), 160-177. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01425692.2019.1697206>

Spoden, C., Fleischer, J., & Frey, A. (2020). Person misfit, text anxiety, and test-taking motivation in a large-scale mathematics proficiency test for self-evaluation. *ELSEVIER*, 67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2020.100910>

- Sujan. (2023, June 15). What is organizing? Definition, features, principles, process, and importance. Tyonote. <https://tyonote.com/organizing/>
- Sullivan, J. (2019). Teaching students how to ask for help. Edutopia. <https://www.edutopia.org/article/teaching-students-how-ask-help/>
- Sutik, Masitoh, S., & Mariono, A. (2022). Digital learning improves problem-solving and self-regulated learning skills for kindergarten children. *NeuroQuantology*, 20(11), 5070-5075. <https://doi.org/10.14704/nq.2022.20.11.NQ66514>
- Sweller, J. (1993). Some cognitive processes and their consequences for the organization and presentation of information. *Australian Journal of Psychology*, 45(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00049539308259112>
- Team, W. (2023, August 25). Cultivating critical thinking for problem solving. Project Management. <https://www.wrike.com/blog/cultivating-critical-thinking>
- Tohir, M. (2019). Hasil PISA indonesia tahun 2018 turun dibanding tahun 2015. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/8Q9VY>
- Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study TIMSS (2019) <https://timssandpirls.bc.edu/timss2019/>
- Widodo, S. A., Darhim, D., & Ikhwanudin, T. (2018). Improving mathematical problem solving skills through visual media. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/948/1/012004>
- Williams, J., Wallace, T. B., & Sung, H. (2018). Providing choice in middle grade classrooms: An exploratory study of enactment variability and student reflection. *Journal of Early Adolescence*, 36(4), 527-550. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0272431615570057>
- Winkler, C., Fust, A., & Jenert, T. (2021). From entrepreneurial experience to expertise: A self-regulated learning perspective. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 61(4), 2071-2096. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00472778.2021.1883041>
- Yang, D., Chen, P., Wang, H., Wang, K., & Huang, R. (2022). Teachers' autonomy support and student engagement: A systematic literature review of longitudinal studies. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.925955>
- Yong, T. H., & Sokumaran, N. (2023). Exploring self-regulated learning through differentiated feedback. *Cogent Education*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2212113>
- Zhao, J., & Qin, Y. (2021). Perceived teacher autonomy support and students' deep learning: The mediating role of self-efficacy and the moderating role of perceived peer support. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.652796>
- Zorfass, J., & Gray, T. (2023). Organizing patterns in mathematics. LD Online. <https://www.ldonline.org/ld-topics/math-dyscalculia/organizing-patterns-mathematics>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Princess Kaye B. Martinez

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Deveyvon L. Espinosa, PhD

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines